

DIFFERENTIAL IMPACT OF GENDER AND LOCATION ON TEACHERS' IMPLEMENTATION OF CONTINUOUS ASSESSMENT IN BASIC SCHOOLS IN DELTA STATE

ISIORHOVOJA, Serome Peter¹, Prof. P. U Osadebe² and
Professor P.A.U. OSSAI³

^{1,2&3}Department of Guidance and Counselling (Measurement and Evaluation
Unit), Faculty of Education, Delta State University, Abraka

ABSTRACT

The study examined the differential impact of gender and location on teachers' implementation of continuous assessment in basic schools in Delta State. For the purpose of this study, three research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. An expo-facto research design was adopted for the study, and 13600 public primary school teachers in Delta State make up the study's population. The sample size of 486 primary school teachers picked from 54 primary schools was utilised. The sample size was (486 primary school teachers selected from 45 primary schools. The multi-stage sampling procedure was used in selecting the sample for the study due to the heterogeneous nature of the population. A questionnaire with the title "Continuous Assessment Implementation Scale (CAIS)" was the instrument used for data collection. This was subjected to a reliability test using Cronbach Alpha, and a reliability coefficient of 0.78 was obtained. The research questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation, while an independent sample t-test were used to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings obtained from the study showed that basic school teachers in Delta State are implementing continuous assessment to a large extent, there is no significant difference between male and female basic teachers' implementation of continuous assessment in Delta State, there is no significant difference between urban and rural basic teachers' implementation of continuous assessment in Delta State. On the basis of the findings and conclusion of the study, it was recommended, among others, teachers should incorporate diverse and student-centered evaluation methods such as project-based assessments and peer evaluations to ensure a comprehensive understanding of students' progress.

Keywords: Gender, location, and implementation Continuous Assessment

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, education has been widely recognised as a key instrument for equipping young individuals with the necessary knowledge and skills to prepare them for the future. This journey begins from the very start, with basic education laying the foundation for future success. Basic education refers to the fundamental knowledge and skills that individuals acquire during their formative years. It includes primary education, secondary education, and sometimes post-secondary education. The primary goal of this stage of education is to develop a strong foundation in reading, writing, mathematics, and critical thinking. Basic education serves as the building blocks upon which future knowledge and skills are built. It provides a solid foundation for reading, writing, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities. These fundamental skills are not only essential for academic success but also for life outside the realm of formal education. Basic education is the foundational level of education that provides the essential knowledge and skills needed for lifelong learning and development. In Nigeria, it typically includes Six years of formal education, typically for children aged 6 to 11, where they are taught core subjects like reading, writing, arithmetic, and general knowledge, and three years of schooling following primary education, focusing on expanding students' knowledge and preparing them for more specialised studies in the senior secondary level. The nine years of the 9-3-4 system are structured in a way that combines primary education and junior secondary education to form basic education.

The objectives of basic education in Nigeria are centred on providing foundational knowledge and skills essential for holistic child development, preparing learners for lifelong learning, and equipping them for active participation in society. According to the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013), these objectives include the promotion of literacy, numeracy, and communication skills as fundamental tools for learning. Basic education also aims to develop learners' problem-solving abilities and critical thinking skills, fostering creativity and innovation. Furthermore, it emphasises moral and civic education to instill values such as discipline, hard work, integrity, and patriotism, ensuring that learners grow into responsible citizens. Another significant objective is to reduce illiteracy, ignorance, and poverty by providing universal access to education, with particular attention to gender equality and inclusion of marginalised groups. Basic education in Nigeria strives to promote the physical, emotional, and psychological development of the child, ensuring that learners are healthy, well-rounded, and equipped with the skills to interact harmoniously within a diverse society. Finally, it serves as the foundation for vocational training, helping learners acquire basic skills that can be expanded upon in secondary and higher education for economic self-reliance (FRN, 2013).

Teachers play a critical role in achieving basic education goals in Nigeria. Their responsibilities extend beyond just delivering the curriculum; they also play a crucial role in assessing the learning process that takes place in schools. Educational assessment is designed to provide the needed feedback teachers and other educational stakeholders require in maximising the outcomes of educational efforts. The teaching and learning process, according to Walde (2016), requires continuous follow-up, and the educational process calls for frequent assessment as society depends on it for the achievement of her goals. The National Policy of Education (2014) stated that educational assessment and evaluation shall be liberalised by being based, in whole or in part, on continuous assessment of the progress of the individual. Continuous assessment (CA) is an educational evaluation system used to measure students' progress and performance over time through a variety of methods, rather

than relying solely on a single final examination. It is an integral part of modern education systems, particularly in Nigeria, where it has been embedded in the National Policy on Education to ensure a holistic approach to evaluating student achievement. The essence of continuous assessment is to provide a more comprehensive and ongoing picture of students' learning and development. It typically includes a variety of assessment techniques such as quizzes, classwork, homework, projects, assignments, practical work, and oral presentations. The evaluation is spread over a period of time, allowing for feedback, reflection, and improvement. By regularly assessing students, teachers can identify areas of strength and weakness, offering timely interventions and support where needed. Continuous assessment evaluates not just cognitive abilities (e.g., knowledge of facts) but also practical skills, creativity, critical thinking, and attitudes, providing a broader measure of a student's abilities.

Quality assessment is as important as education itself; as a result, many countries, including Nigeria, are constantly developing assessment initiatives and policies to improve the quality of education. Continuous assessment is one viable assessment platform through which stakeholders in the education sector can carry out valid and reliable assessment to know how well the goals of the country's education are being achieved. Continuous assessment is a systematic and objective procedure for determining the extent to which a learner has performed in all the expected areas of change in behaviour from his first day in an educational programme. It is a means of carrying out assessment formally within the classroom while making a valid judgement about an individual learner's progress within a particular subject area, and it usually occurs on a regular and continuous basis (Ossai, 2020). Continuous assessment procedures require a careful accumulation of information in areas where changes are expected to take place for the purpose of guiding and sharpening learners (Idowu & Esere, 2009). Worukwu and Etokeren (2022) further opined that information obtained from a holistic assessment serves as evidence of learners' performance, which in turn informs decision-making by stakeholders.

Continuous assessment takes into account all learners' activities in the three domains of learning from the beginning to the end of the school year. This can be achieved using various assessment techniques to ensure an acceptable level of comprehensiveness. Okeke and Ohia (2013) viewed continuous assessment as a regular evaluation of both input and output in teaching and learning activities in order to assess the extent to which the goals and objectives of such activities are achieved. Orherhueta (2021) defined continuous assessment as a procedure that integrates learning and teaching with assessment, offering a more comprehensive evaluation of learners' performance.

The expectation of continuous assessment has not been fully met as it is not being practiced the way it was stipulated in the national policy on education. Parents, guidance, and other education stakeholders expect certain changes in the behaviour of learners based on what they are exposed to over time in a desirable direction. These changes are expected to occur in knowledge, attitude, affection, and manipulative skills. According to Uyanah et al. (2021), the level at which continuous assessment is implemented determines the extent to which the education of the citizens is successful. Uyanah et al. (2021) further posited that teachers who are at the helm of affairs in this policy implementation must ensure that assessment is carried out periodically and in the three domains of learning behaviour, which will form the basis for decisions to be taken about the learner.

However, teachers' implementation of continuous assessment seems to be awful in recent times. Berihu (2016) opined that most teachers overdepend on very few assessment

techniques, most especially tests, which, in most cases, measure progress only in the cognitive domain with total neglect of the non-cognitive areas of learning. Ntu and Ojating (2018) stated that the comprehensive quality of continuous assessment is jeopardized when teachers place too much emphasis on the cognitive learning behaviour. Kapambwe (2010) examined the challenges of continuous assessment implementation and found out that teachers are of the wrong view that continuous assessment is synonymous with continuous testing. Emphasizing more on the importance of teachers' role in the implementation of continuous assessment, Molid and Rohaya (2013) stated that proper implementation of continuous assessment depends on the teacher's working knowledge and skills of the assessment procedures.

In Delta State, the implementation of continuous assessment by teachers is influenced by factors such as gender and location. This document explores the impact of these factors on teachers' implementation of continuous assessment in basic schools.

Demographic features are qualities that explain the status or standing of people or a person (Ghaleb et al., 2021). These attributes include gender, location, class size, qualification, socio-economic status, ethnicity, age, and working experience, among others. Studies such as Francisco's (2020) have been able to link teachers' personal demographic characteristics to their job performance. The study found a significant contribution of teachers' personal characteristics, such as gender and age. As far as continuous assessment implementation is concerned, the differential impact of teachers' demography is key. In Delta State, the implementation of continuous assessment by teachers at the basic school could be influenced by factors such as teachers' gender and location.

Teacher's gender is another variable this study will be dwelling on. Asodike (2016) sees gender as a word used to describe the features of men and women constructed socially, while sex refers to those features biologically determined; it is simply being male or female. According to Luga (2016), gender is defined as socially and culturally constructed roles for men and women. The findings from Luga's (2016) study showed that gender predicted teachers' effective supervisory practices in secondary schools to a large extent. Dien et al. (2022) opined that female teachers tend to be more effective than their male counterparts. This could be due to societal perceptions of teaching as a female profession, as noted by Babo and Mustapha (2020). In a profession dominated by one gender, implementation of continuous assessment may be compromised as these genders have their own peculiar challenges that may interfere with their day-to-day activities.

The location of a teacher is another characteristic of the teacher. The location a teacher is operating continuous assessment from can influence how well he holistically implements continuous assessment. The location of schools can be urban or rural. Urban areas are places with a high population density of people with basic social amenities of life, such as big markets, banks, and well-equipped schools, among others. Rural areas, on the other hand, are places with low population density with minimal social amenities. Lack of social amenities in rural areas hinders educational services, since such social amenities serve as motivational factors that encourage teachers to do their best in discharging their official duties (Awodun&Oyeniyi, 2018). As a result of the differences that exist in the structure of the urban and rural areas, there may be discrepancies in urban and rural teachers' implementation of continuous assessment. The teacher's location may influence the implementation of continuous assessment; as different locations have their own unique challenges. Urban teachers may complain of population surge and lack of space, among others. Rural teachers,

on the other hand, may complain of a lack of basic infrastructure to carry out continuous assessment, poor attendance, and a poor road network, among others.

Statement of the Problem

Educational assessment appears to be the central core of the teaching and learning process. This is because learners' academic abilities form the basis on which decisions about the entire school system including the learners are made. Continuous assessment was introduced to complement the classical one-shot examination in schools and to reduce its negative implication on the system. Consequently, the purpose of this new assessment pathway is expected to manifest in teachers' assessment procedures. Afemikhe (2015) described continuous assessment in Nigeria as counterfeit due to its shabby mode of implementation. Shabby activities such as poor records keeping, lack of practical activities, the use of few assessment tools, too much concentration on the cognitive domain, wrong assessment tools, examination malpractice among other forms of wrong practices as pointed out by research findings like that of Ashenafi (2018), and as observed by the researcher, are major challenges to continuous assessment implementation.

Teachers' demographic variables as determinants of quality education have become recurrent issues. This is because, Teachers are major instruments to the successful execution of any educational programme engaged in by the government of any society (Ekperi, 2018). The success of continuous assessment implementation to a large extent depends on the teacher; as a result, the differences in the demographic characteristics of these teachers may interfere with their day to day class room activities which include assessment. In light of the above, this study assessed the differential impact of gender and location on teachers' implementation of continuous assessment in basic schools in delta state.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in the study:

1. To what extent do primary school teachers apply continuous assessment in Delta State?
2. What is the difference in continuous assessment implementation between male and female primary school teachers in Delta State?
3. What is the difference in continuous assessment implementation between urban and rural primary school teachers in Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested in the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the implementation of continuous assessment between male and female primary school teachers in Delta State.
2. There is no significant difference in the implementation of continuous assessment between urban and rural primary school teachers in Delta State.

Research Methods

The ex-post facto research design was used in this study. 13600 public primary school teachers in Delta State make up the study's population, according to data from the Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education's Department of Planning, Research, and Statistics in Asaba (2022). The sample size of 486 primary school teachers picked from 54 primary schools was utilised. Because the population was diverse, a multi-stage sampling technique was used to

choose the research sample. Initially, the study population was proportionally stratified by the researcher. Because Delta State had senatorial districts, quota sampling was used. A simple random sample approach to balloting was employed to choose three (3) local government areas from each of the three senatorial districts. Following that, six elementary schools in each of the local governments were chosen at random. This amounted to the 54 in total that Delta State covered. A total of 486 primary school teachers were chosen for the research in the third stage, with nine teachers chosen from each school. The tool utilised in this investigation was a questionnaire. The questionnaire was modelled after Orherhueta (2020). portions A and B comprise its two portions.

The demographic factors in Section A, sometimes referred to as the respondents' personal data, include gender and school location. On the other hand, Section B uses the Continuous Assessment Implementation Scale (CAIS). The scale consists of 23 items organized according to continuous evaluation components. The researcher will advise instructors to identify their degree of agreement or disagreement on a four-point scale for each item on the scale, which is given as a statement. Disagree (D) = 2, severely disagree (SD) = 1, strongly agree (SA) = 4, agree (A) = 3. Expert opinions were used to validate the research tool. The supervisors of the researcher, who are specialists in measuring and assessing face and content validity, were shown the questionnaire. In accordance with the school's mandate for continual evaluation, the tool was thoroughly examined. In order to evaluate the internal consistency of the tool, elementary school teachers in Edo State's Orhionmwon Local Government Area were given fifty (50) copies of the questionnaire. The dependability technique of Cronbach's alpha was used with the given data. For the instrument, a coefficient of 0.789 was discovered. The researcher and two research assistants conducted the questionnaire in person. All study issues were addressed using the mean and standard deviation, and hypotheses were tested using an independent sample t-test. Responses below 2.5 were rejected; a mean value of 2.5 above served as the standard for approval. Using SPSS, all hypotheses were analysed at the.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Research Question One

To what extent do basic school teachers implement continuous assessment in Delta State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Showing the Extent to which Basic Education Teachers Implement Continuous Assessment.

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	I score pupils/students during class room activities	3.07	0.84	Agreed
2.	I monitor learners learning progress in relation to learning objectives	3.2	0.76	Agreed
3.	I re-teach a topic if not well understood by learners	3.13	0.72	Agreed
4.	I involve learners in assignment after instructions.	3.25	0.66	Agreed
5.	I involve learners in practical after teaching a theme	2.38	0.93	Disagreed
6.	I assess learners value/moral systems	3.16	0.76	Agreed
7.	I assess learners mental skills/ abilities	3.2	0.7	Agreed
8.	I engage learners in peer assessment to enable them learn from each other	2.99	0.73	Agreed
9.	My school have a functional continuous assessment committee	2.42	0.97	Disagreed
10.	I assign scores to all assignments I give to learners	3.04	0.86	Agreed
11.	I return marked test scripts to learners	3.1	0.82	Agreed
12.	I returned marked assignment to learners	3.41	0.61	Agreed
13.	I give learners notice before issuing test	3.31	0.79	Agreed
14.	I use marking scheme when scoring learners	3.15	0.87	Agreed
15.	I record continuous assessment scores properly	3.41	0.7	Agreed
16.	I keep continuous assessment scores safe for future purposes	3.37	0.62	Agreed
17.	I use information from continuous assessment activities to guide learners.	3.21	0.68	Agreed
18.	I keep records of learners as I observe them	3.07	0.82	Agreed
19.	I adjust instructions any time learners finds it difficult to understand a taught topic	3.16	0.62	Agreed
20.	I refer academic challenge learners for guidance and counselling	3.15	0.69	Agreed
21.	I use feedback from continuous assessment to improve learning progress	3.18	0.73	Agreed
22.	I communicate assessment results to parents/guidance.	2.43	0.93	Disagreed
23.	I give career guidance to learners based on their performance	2.95	0.83	Agreed
	Grand Mean	3.08	0.77	Agreed

Mean bench mark=2.50 N=486

Table 1 shows the mean scores of individual items as responded to by primary school teachers. The table also shows a grand mean of 3.08, which is higher than the bench mark of 2.5; this indicates that basic school teachers in Delta State are implementing continuous assessment to a very large extent. Items 13, 15, and 16 recorded the highest mean values of 3.31, 3.41, and 3.37, respectively. This shows that the majority of the teachers follow continuous assessment guidelines, as they give learners notice before assessing them, record continuous assessment scores properly, and keep continuous assessment records safe for future use. However, items 5, 9, and 22 recorded the lowest mean score of 2.38, 2.42, and 2.43, respectively. This indicates that most basic school teachers do not involve their learners in practical activities, most schools do not have a functional continuous assessment committee, and most teachers do not communicate assessment results to parents or guidance.

Research Question Two

What is the difference between male and female basic school teachers' implementation of continuous assessment in Delta State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of the differences between male and female basic school teachers Implementation of Continuous Assessment in Delta State.

S/N.	ITEMS	Male (N=212)		Female(N=274)	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
1.	I score pupils/students during class room activities	3.09	0.82	3.05	0.86
2.	I monitor learners learning progress in relation to learning objectives	3.25	0.75	3.16	0.77
3.	I re-teach a topic if not well understood by learners	3.16	0.73	3.11	0.71
4.	I involve learners in assignment after instructions.	3.34	0.6	3.18	0.69
5.	I involve learners in practical after teaching a theme	2.42	0.94	2.35	0.92
6.	I assess learners value/moral systems	3.18	0.72	3.14	0.79
7.	I assess learners mental skills/ abilities	3.24	0.66	3.18	0.73
8.	I engage learners in peer assessment to enable them learn from each other	3.01	0.72	2.97	0.74
9.	My school have a functional continuous assessment committee	2.47	0.99	2.38	0.96
10.	I assign scores to all assignments I give to learners	3.01	0.82	3.06	0.88
11.	I return marked test scripts to learners	3.12	0.79	3.09	0.85
12.	I returned marked assignment to learners	3.42	0.57	3.4	0.64
13.	I give learners notice before issuing test	3.37	0.78	3.26	0.79
14.	I use marking scheme when scoring learners	3.17	0.89	3.14	0.85
15.	I record continuous assessment scores properly	3.48	0.64	3.36	0.74
16.	I keep continuous assessment scores safe for future purposes	3.37	0.6	3.37	0.63
17.	I use information from continuous assessment activities to guide learners.	3.22	0.66	3.2	0.69
18.	I keep records of learners as I observe them	3.14	0.79	3.03	0.82
19.	I adjust instructions any time learners finds it difficult to understand a taught topic	3.17	0.63	3.14	0.61
20.	I refer academic challenge learners for guidance and counselling	3.19	0.71	3.14	0.68
21.	I use feedback from continuous assessment to improve learning progress	3.2	0.72	3.17	0.73
22.	I communicate assessment results to parents/guidance.	2.48	0.96	2.46	0.93
23.	I give career guidance to learners based on their performance	2.96	0.81	2.95	0.85
Grand Mean		3.11	0.75	3.06	0.78

Table 2 shows item by item results of the differences between male and female basic school teachers' implementation of continuous assessment in Delta State. The result showed a grand mean of 3.11 for male teachers and 3.06 for female teachers with a difference of 0.05. The differences in the mean value shows that female teachers implement continuous assessment slightly more than their male counterpart to some extent.

Research Question Three

What is the difference between urban and rural basic school teachers' implementation of continuous assessment in Delta State?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of the differences between urban and rural basic school teachers Implementation of Continuous Assessment in Delta State.

S/N.	ITEMS	Urban (N=238)		Rural N=248)	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
1.	I score pupils/students during class room activities	3.04	0.88	3.10	0.81
2.	I monitor learners learning progress in relation to learning objectives	3.23	0.72	3.17	0.79
3.	I re-teach a topic if not well understood by learners	3.13	0.7	3.13	0.73
4.	I involve learners in assignment after instructions.	3.25	0.67	3.25	0.65
5.	I involve learners in practical after teaching a theme	2.42	0.94	2.34	0.92
6.	I assess learners value/moral systems	3.18	0.75	3.14	0.77
7.	I assess learners mental skills/ abilities	3.22	0.68	3.19	0.72
8.	I engage learners in peer assessment to enable them learn from each other	2.97	0.71	3.01	0.75
9.	My school have a functional continuous assessment committee	2.44	0.95	2.4	0.99
10.	I assign scores to all assignments I give to learners	3.07	0.87	3.01	0.84
11.	I return marked test scripts to learners	3.12	0.84	3.09	0.81
12.	I returned marked assignment to learners	3.46	0.61	3.35	0.6
13.	I give learners notice before issuing test	3.31	0.8	3.3	0.79
14.	I use marking scheme when scoring learners	3.17	0.84	3.14	0.89
15.	I record continuous assessment scores properly	3.45	0.63	3.38	0.76
16.	I keep continuous assessment scores safe for future purposes	3.43	0.55	3.31	0.67
17.	I use information from continuous assessment activities to guide learners.	3.19	0.67	3.23	0.68
18.	I keep records of learners as I observe them	3.09	0.77	3.04	0.86
19.	I adjust instructions any time learners finds it difficult to understand a taught topic	3.09	0.66	3.22	0.56
20.	I refer academic challenge learners for guidance and counseling	3.16	0.72	3.15	0.66
21.	I use feedback from continuous assessment to improve learning progress	3.18	0.69	3.17	0.76
22.	I communicate assessment results to parents/guidance.	2.47	0.93	2.39	0.93
23.	I give career guidance to learners based on their performance	2.96	0.83	2.94	0.83
Grand Mean		3.09	0.76	3.06	0.77

Mean Bench mark=2.50

Table 3 shows item by item results of the differences between urban and rural basic school teachers' implementation of continuous assessment in Delta State. The result showed a grand mean of 3.09 for urban teachers and 3.06 for rural teachers with a difference of 0.03. The differences in the mean value shows that urban teachers urban teachers implement continuous assessment slightly more than their counterparts in the rural area.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant differences between male and female basic school teachers' implementation of continuous assessment in Delta State.

Table 4: Independent t -test of difference between Male and Female basic school Teachers' Implementation of Continuous Assessment in Delta State.

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-cal.	Sig,(2-tailed)	Decision
Males Teacher	212	3.11	0.34			
Females Teachers	274	3.06	0.39	484	1.51	0.133
Total	486					Not significant

Table 4 shows a t test statistic used to determine the level of significance of the difference between male and female basic school teachers' implementation of continuous assessment in Delta State. The revealed a t= 1.51 and p value of .133 which is greater than 0.05 alpha level. Based on this, the null hypothesis accepted. This means that there is no significant difference between male and female basic teachers' implementation of continuous assessment in Delta State.

Hypothesis 2: there is no significant difference between urban and rural basic school teachers' implementation of continuous assessment in Delta State.

Table 5: Independent Sample t-test of Difference Between Urban and Rural basic school Teachers' Implementation of Continuous Assessment in Delta State.

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-cal.	Sig,(2-tailed)	Decision
Urban Teacher	238	3.09	0.35			
Rural Teachers	248	3.07	0.39	484	.68	0.499
Total	486					Not significant

Table 5 shows a t test statistic in determining the level of significance of the difference between urban and rural basic teachers' implementation of continuous assessment in Delta State. The p value of .499 is more than 0.05 alpha level. Based on this, the null hypothesis was accepted. This means that there is no significant difference between urban and rural basic school teachers' implementation of continuous assessment in basic and secondary schools in Delta State.

Discussion of findings

The Extent of basic Schools Teachers' Implementation of Continuous Assessment

The first finding of this study revealed that the extent of teachers' implementation of continuous assessment in basic schools is high. This shows that the majority of the teachers

agreed that they are implementing continuous assessment in basic schools in Delta State. This finding shed light on the fact that teachers in primary and secondary schools are actively embracing and incorporating continuous assessment practices into their teaching methodologies. One possible explanation for the high extent of teachers' implementation of continuous assessment could be the growing recognition of its numerous benefits. Teachers are becoming more aware that continuous assessment enhances student engagement, motivation, and metacognitive skills. This finding is in line with Chiziwa, (2022) and pals (2023) who revealed that primary school teachers' implementation of continuous assessment is improving due to the recognition of its numerous benefits and deeper understanding of its concepts as it fosters the development of critical thinking abilities among students.

Differences between Male and Female Basic School Teachers' Implementation of Continuous Assessment

The second finding of this research revealed that male teachers in basic schools do not implement continuous assessment more than their female counterparts; hence, no significant difference existed between male and female teachers on the implementation of continuous assessment in basic schools in Delta State. This implies that teachers sex does not have much role to play in the implementation of continuous assessment. One possible explanation for the absence of a significant difference in the implementation of continuous assessment between male and female teachers in Delta State is that there may be other factors at play that are not directly related to gender. Factors such as the training, support, and resources available to teachers can impact their implementation of continuous assessment, regardless of their gender. This finding aligns with that of Osadebe (2015) and Amobi (2020) who revealed in their individual studies that there is no significant difference between male and female lecturers on the implementation of continuous assessment. This finding, however, disagrees with Okon and Archibong (2015), Mezieob et al. (2012) and Marcus and Joseph (2014) who in their various studies found significant differences between male and female teachers and lecturers' implementation of continuous assessment.

Difference between urban and rural basic school teachers' implementation of continuous assessment.

The third finding of the study showed that differences do not exist between urban and rural teachers' implementation of continuous assessment in primary schools in Delta State. This is an indication that location has no interference with teachers' implementation of continuous assessment; hence, teachers, irrespective of location, can effectively operate the continuous assessment mode. This could be a result of the fact that teachers' conditions of service are the same regardless of their location.

This finding is in line with that of Osadebe and Uvietesivwi (2018) and Ezeudu et al. (2014) who revealed that teachers' locations do not differ in their implementation of continuous assessment and geography students' achievement. The study of Ilogho (2015), Kuyenum and Fejokwu (2018) and ovat et al. (2021) they reported in their respective studies that significant differences existed between urban and rural locations and as such, location influences both students achievement and teachers job performance.

Conclusion

The study examined the differential impact of gender and location on the implementation of continuous assessment by basic school teachers in Delta State. Based on

the findings, the following conclusions were drawn: To a large extent, basic school teachers in Delta State are effectively implementing continuous assessment. This indicates that continuous assessment practices have been widely adopted and integrated into teaching methodologies across the state. There is no significant difference between male and female teachers who implement continuous assessment. This suggests that gender does not play a significant role in determining how teachers engage with continuous assessment practices in Delta State's basic schools. Similarly, there is no significant difference in continuous assessment implementation between urban and rural teachers. This finding highlights that location, whether urban or rural, does not influence the extent to which teachers in Delta State implement continuous assessment. Overall, the study concludes that continuous assessment is being implemented uniformly across gender and geographical locations in Delta State, reflecting equitable practices in the educational system concerning continuous assessment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- I. Teachers should incorporate diverse and student-centered evaluation methods such as project-based assessments and peer evaluations to ensure a comprehensive understanding of students' progress.
- II. School heads should regularly monitor continuous assessment practices and provide the necessary resources and support, ensuring consistency and quality across the school.
- III. The Ministry should organize state-wide professional development programs on continuous assessment, ensuring teachers, especially in rural areas, receive training and support.

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